

CHARACTERIZATION OF MULTISTACK CIGS, (CUGA/IN/SE...), ON MO COATED SLG BY USING THE IN-LINE SPUTTERING SYSTEM

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Abstract

The Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ polycrystalline thin films were prepared by using a novel precursor. The Se inserted precursors were annealed in a furnace system without supplying Se source. In order to overcome the several problems found in a selenized Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ layer such as voids formation, rough surface and uncontrollability of MoSe₂ thickness, the precisely determined amount of Se was sandwiched inbetween the Cu-In-Ga metal slabs with different distribution scheme. By concentrating the Se layer near the top part of the multilayer precursor, we successfully obtained CIGS free of interface voids and with minimized MoSe₂ thickness less than 100nm. It was also found that the Ga concentration is increasing towards the surface of CIGS selenized from the multilayer precursor. The proposed method is expected to provide a simple and safe process for high quality CIGS photovoltaic absorber layer.

1. Introduction

Cu(In,Ga)Se₂ (CIGS)-based thin film solar cell has already been partially commercialized due to its high cell efficiency. CIGS thin film solar cells exhibit an efficiency of 20% at a laboratory scale[1], which is the highest efficiency ever reported for any kind of thin film solar cells. This high efficiency was obtained by the three stages process developed by NREL. Since this technique does not guarantee a good stoichiometry over a large area, now most research is oriented towards processes that are easily scalable and that are able to produce low cost and efficient modules.

Sputtering is one of the vacuum techniques applicable for the large-area inline manufacturing process which is required for low-cost large-area thin-film photovoltaic module.[2].

The conventional selenization process is using Se containing vapor phase to selenize the metal only precursor, CuInGa, which is called a two step process. During the process, Se is supplied from the top surface of the precursor and hence the resulting film will undergo a Ga grading problem due to the different reaction rate of the precursor elements with Se, void formation, and the difficulty of controlling the MoSe₂ thickness.

In this study, in order to overcome the above mentioned problems, a precursor was produced in a form of multi-stacks of CuGa/In/Se on Mo-coated soda-lime glass substrate using in-line sputter system equipped with a Se evaporator. The multi-stack precursor was annealed to form a CIGS thin film in inert gas ambient.

2. Experimental

Precursor deposition

Fig. 1. A schematic of in-line sputtering system with three-source sputters and a Se evaporator

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The Se inserted precursor films were deposited by three-source DC magnetron sputtering onto Mo-coated soda-lime glass substrate by using the In-line sputter system as shown in Fig. 1.

The pure In and CuGa(Ga,24wt%) dual targets of 3 inch diameter with 3mm thickness were used. The base pressure was 7×10^{-7} Torr and working pressure was 5m Torr at room temperature. A drum tray which is used for substrate holder was rotated at 1/3 rpm for fabricating the multi-stacks of CuGa/In/Se. All four constituent elements (Cu, In, Ga and Se) were deposited by sputtering CuGa and In and evaporating Se.

Also, the thickness of precursor with Se was adjusted by DC power at Se boat and amount of it. In order to compare the Ga-profile, void formation and thickness of MoSe₂, the position of inserted Se inbetween CIG was intentionally adjusted with a fixed DC power at In and CuGa targets.

Selenization

The selenization was carried out in a resistive heated quartz furnace. A selenization temperature was 500°C, and the ramp-up speed from room temperature to the target temperature was 22.7°C/min[3]. Once the temperature reached 500°C, the selenization reaction was induced for 5 minutes, then cooling was carried out over 20 minutes.

In order to restrain loss of the In, which is known to re-evaporate in the form of volatile In₂Se compound resulting in copper-rich absorber surface [4,5], the precursor was capped with a sodalime glass during the selenization reaction as shown in Fig 2. The cover glass was easily removed after cooling the sample.

Fig. 2. A schematic of the multilayer precursor and selenization.

Measurements

Both the multi-stack precursors and the CIGS films were analyzed with X-ray diffractometer to check the crystalline properties. A scanning electron microscope (SEM) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) were used to examine the morphology variation and the composition profile.

3. Results and discussion

Fig. 3. The SEM micrographs showing (a) rough surface morphology and (b) cross-section of CIGS selenized using Se vapor.

Figure 3 shows the surface and cross sectional morphology of CIGS obtained by selenizing the metal-only precursor using Se vapor. There are three main features such as interface voids between CIGS and Mo, formation of thick MoSe₂ on top of Mo, and the rough surface. In the two step process, Se must be diffused from top of metal precursor and the metal components should move to the surface, resulting in the void formation due to the mass transport across the distance as much as the

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precursor thickness. Unlike the co-evaporated CIGS, a two step selenized CIGS usually has very rough surface due to either In agglomeration or volume expansion during the selenization reaction.

The normal reaction time using Se vapor is usually longer than using highly reactive selenide gas such as H_2Se or diethylselenide (DESe) due to higher binding energy [6]. Therefore, normally the highly excessive Se environment is adopted for promoting selenization rate. Upon the irregular film morphology described above, the Se excess condition makes it difficult to control the thickness of $MoSe_2$, which otherwise should be minimized to reduce the series resistance of the solar cell.

In order to overcome the problems mentioned above including voids formation and controllability of $MoSe_2$ layer, we suggest a novel precursor structure, where the exact amount of Se required to fully selenize the metallic precursor is inserted inbetween CIG layers.

The X-ray diffraction pattern and SEM images of the as-deposited (CuGa/In/Se) multilayer precursor are shown in Fig. 4. The X-ray diffraction peaks indicates the presence of Cu_4In , free In and CuSe phase only. And Fig. 4(b) shows smoother surface morphology without any trace of heavily agglomerated In island. Fig. 4(c) shows an exemplary multilayer precursor where the Se layer is evenly distributed across the precursor thickness (the relatively dark line tells the location of Se layer).

Fig. 4. X-ray diffraction spectrum of CIGS precursor layer (a) and The SEM micrographs showing (b) a typical surface morphology and (c) cross-section stacks structure between CuInGa and Se.

Fig. 5. The SEM micrographs showing (a) cross-section of CIGS and (b) a surface morphology with cover glass.

Fig. 5 shows the SEM images of CIGS obtained from annealing the multilayer precursor shown in Fig. 4 at $500^\circ C$ for 10min in 1atm N_2 environment.

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Compared to the CIGS shown in Fig. 3, the film surface becomes more uniform due to the minimized mass transport by stacking thin slabs of Se and metals.

On the other hand, some of small and large voids were observed from the plan view of the CIGS. The void generation in CIGS synthesized under Se-abundant environment may be attributed to the liquid Cu_{2-x}Se phase formation promoting grain growth due to the liquid phase assisted diffusion [8]. The voids should be removed, otherwise the device fabricated using the current absorber layer would have very low shunt resistance and hence low fill factor. And the thick MoSe_2 of approximately 500nm, shown in Fig. 3(a), is another aspect of the excess Se.

With the intention to resolve the above issues, the total amount of Se is reduced and also the large fraction of Se is concentrated near top surface as shown in Fig. 6(a).

Fig. 6. The SEM images; (a) cross-section of multi-layer precursor, (b) cross-section and (c) surface morphology of CIGS annealed with biased Se layer.

After annealing of the precursor with the biased Se distribution, it is clear that the surface voids and even the surface morphology of CIGS were considerably improved. Furthermore, MoSe_2 thickness is greatly reduced down to 50~100nm, with which a device performance would not be affected [9].

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Fig. 7. X-ray diffraction patterns of CIGS with (a) a biased Se layer and (b) uniformly inserted Se.

Fig 7 shows the X-ray diffraction patterns of the annealed CIGS with different Se distribution. The phases of CIGS, Mo, and MoSe₂ were found for both films. It is noteworthy that the (220)/(112) peak ratio of CIGS with a biased Se layer is greater than that of a uniformly distributed Se layer. The reason, however, why the Se distribution affects the preferred orientation is not clear yet.

Fig 8. The EDS line-scan spectrums of each element in CIGS obtained with the biased Se layer. The data were recorded along the (a) direction.

Fig. 8 shows each element intensity of line scan data in annealed CIGS with Mo layer in EDS according to (a) direction. A selenized CIGS usually has a single-graded bandgap increasing from the surface to the back contact due to the different reaction rate of Ga and In with Se. It is well known that Ga will be pushed and concentrated near Mo back contact during selenization[10]. However, from the CIGS annealed with the biased Se layer, it was found that the concentration of Ga was increased near the surface area as shown in Fig. 8. Because, the Se reaction with CIG took place from the inside of the multilayer precursor, Ga was repelled towards the surface. . Even the double graded Ga profile, which is believed to be essential parameter for high efficiency in polycrystalline solar cell, could be obtained by simply adjusting the deposition sequence of Cu-Ga/In/Se.

4. Conclusion

The several main problems are expected to be easily resolvable by fabricating novel multi stack precursor.

In this study, a novel architecture of Cu-In-Ga/Se stack for synthesizing CIGS compound semiconductor was tried using in-line sputtering system, where multi layers of Se was sandwiched inbetween thin slab of Cu-In-Ga. By adjusting the amount of Se required for complete selenization of Cu-In-Ga and concentrating most of Se near top part of the multilayer precursor, the voids were successfully eliminated and MoSe₂ thickness was minimized. And also, the beneficial Ga profile near top surface of CIGS was achieved due to the location of Se. The novel method suggested in this study is expected to be able to overcome the several selenization issues encountered in the commercial two-step CIGS formation process.

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